

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

UDC 519.83

FINDING PREFERRED CANDIDATES USING THE MATRIX GAME

Beltadze G.N.,

*Doctor of Physical and Mathematical Sciences, Ph.D., Professor emeritus, Department
Artificial Intelligence Georgian Technical University, 0175 Tbilisi, Georgia*

Giorgobiani J.A.

*PhD in Mathematics, Consultant, Department of Mathematical Modeling
Muskhelishvili Institute of Computational Mathematics of the
Georgian Technical University, 0159 Tbilisi, Georgia*

Abstract

Ranking problem of a multitude $S = \{a_1, \dots, a_m\}$ for small number of competitive candidates is considered in consideration of many $K = \{k_1, \dots, k_n\}$ criteria. Given multitude is requested to be ranked according to diminution of priorities - from advantage to the worse. From the beginning it is implied that the mentioned criteria are equivalent. We discuss the given task as an antagonistic game against nature, that is why we make settlement of problem with the game model against nature. In such case, strategies are competitive candidates. Optimal mixed strategy of first player is counted with the maximin principle, by which candidates will be selected and expected average grade of each candidate $u(a_i) = x_i^* \sum_{j=1}^n u_{ij}$ will be defined through it. We make ranking of the candidates in respect to nonstrict advantage $\succsim$ and use expected average grading criterion: $a_i \succsim a_k \Leftrightarrow u(a_i) \geq u(a_k)$. Relevant examples are given.

Keywords: competitive candidates, ranking, dominant, game, player, utility, matrix game, optimal solution, weight, average.

1. Introduction

In general, the competitive task is as follows: a set of candidates (alternatives) $S = \{a_1, \dots, a_m\}$ is given, and it is required to set priorities on this set, taking into account many criteria, that is, we need to rank the given set according to decreasing priorities - from the best to the worst. We studied this task using the method of hierarchical analysis [1]. Here, the task is to set priorities on the set of candidates of a small group. To solve it, we are guided by a new principle that derives from the principles of game theory, namely, the optimal solution obtained by solving a finite antagonistic game against nature. Such tasks have practical needs, which are found in the case of competition, project evaluation, etc.

Game theory is a mathematical theory of conflict situations [2,3,4,5]. In this theory, a conflict situation is understood as every such situation - an event in which the participating parties strive for a certain goal and have several choices. However, the choice of each side depends on the choice of its opponent, and therefore the degree of achievement of the goal for each player depends on the choice of all participants. Since the participant in the conflict situation - the player - does not have enough information about the opponent's intention, therefore, the decision is made by the methods of game theory under conditions of uncertainty. The goal of the game theory is to develop recommendations for the intelligent behavior of conflict participants, that is, to determine the optimal strategies of the players' behavior.

A game is a mathematical model of the collective behavior of several persons (parties, players). This implies that the interests of the players are different, which creates a conflict. The conflict does not imply an antagonistic confrontation between the parties, but is always related to some kind of disagreement. A conflict situation will be antagonistic if an increase in one party's profit (utility) by some amount leads to a decrease in the other party's profit by the same amount, and vice versa. Therefore, in an antagonistic conflict, the sum of the players' payoffs is zero. Antagonism of interests gives rise to antagonistic conflict and we get an antagonistic game. In case of coincidence of interests, the game will be reduced to cooperation of actions and we get a new class of game - cooperative game. Thus, game theory studies mathematical methods, models and ways of analyzing rational decisions between conflicting parties under conditions of uncertainty.

In game theory, two main types of antagonistic games are distinguished: 1) a game against an opponent; 2) playing against nature. In the first type of games, we are dealing with a well-thought-out reaction of the opponent. Here, the adversary essentially limits the set of desirable outcomes acceptable to the decision maker. In the second type of games, we have a game under conditions of adversarial and at the same time uncertainty, in which only one player is the decision maker (DMP). He strives for the maximum of his utility, and at the same time he does not know what his opponent - nature, will do, because he is not an active

thinking player, but GMP considers him like this. GMP considers that the adversary's goal is to disrupt it so that acceptable expected utility is minimal. We consider such a game.

2. Matrix game model of candidate ranking

Let's make a model of such a game. Let's assume that we want to rank the candidates with advantages, taking into account some signs or signs (criteria). Let's say there is such a set of criteria $K = \{k_1, \dots, k_n\}$. An expert E or a group of experts evaluates each candidate $a_i (i = 1, \dots, m)$ by criteria $k_j (j = 1, \dots, n)$. Let's assume that such an assessment is quantitative, and the criteria are equally important. Mark the candidate's a_i evaluation by criterion k_j with u_{ij} . The number $u_{ij} (i = 1, \dots, m; j = 1, \dots, n)$ represents the candidate's a_i usefulness (satisfaction measure) with the criterion k_j for the expert. Considering the variety of criteria for a given specific task, it is natural to assume that each criterion k_j has a single scale of evaluations

$$u_{ij} \in [\alpha, \beta], 0 \leq \alpha < \beta;$$

$i = 1, \dots, m; j = 1, \dots, n$. In the conditions of the received designations, the evaluations of the candidates S should be presented with the criteria K by means of the following type of H matrix (table)

$$H = \begin{array}{c|cccc} & k_1 & k_2 & \dots & k_n \\ \hline a_1 & u_{11} & u_{12} & \dots & u_{1n} \\ a_2 & u_{21} & u_{22} & \dots & u_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_m & u_{m1} & u_{m2} & \dots & u_{mn} \end{array}, \quad (1)$$

where $u_{ij} \in [\alpha, \beta], 0 \leq \alpha < \beta;$

$i = 1, \dots, m; j = 1, \dots, n$. Based on the table of candidates' evaluations (1), the task of ranking the candidates may be solved in the simplest way according to the decrease of the total evaluations received by the candidates, for example, by the following ratio:

$$a_i \succcurlyeq a_k \Leftrightarrow \sum_{j=1}^n u_{ij} \geq \sum_{j=1}^n u_{kj}, \quad (2)$$

where $\succcurlyeq$ denotes a non-strict preference relation. $\succ$ be the relation of strict superiority, and $\approx$ the relation of equality (equivalence). For example, if a is superior to b , then we will write $a \succ b$, if a is not inferior to - $a \succcurlyeq b$, if a it is equal to b , then $a \approx b$. For example, let's say for four candidates $S = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4\}$ we have transit advantages: a_1 is superior to a_3 , a_3 is superior to a_4 and a_4 is also equal to a_2 . In this case, the ranking of the set S will be written as - $a_1 \succ a_3 \succ a_4 \approx a_2$.

In such case, it is necessary to note the following: according to the theory of utility [6], the evaluation of the candidate participating in the competition is made

by the expert taking into account subjective factors. Therefore, it is not excluded that his evaluations may turn out to be non-objective in order to win a candidate, so that the respective candidate wins. Therefore, the ranking of candidates by the ratio (2) is unacceptable. Therefore, our main interest in solving the given task implies that without using the criterion from the table (1) it is impossible to rank the candidates.

If we assume that (1) both players in the matrix game are intelligent, then the principle of optimality for obtaining maximum utility is the principle of maximin (equilibrium situation) in mixed strategies. According to the basic theorem of game theory, this principle is always realizable, that is, in any matrix game, players have optimal solutions in mixed strategies for every month.

In a matrix game, the optimal decision of the first player in mixed strategies $X^* = (x_1^*, \dots, x_m^*)$ is determined by reaching the maximal $\max_x \min_j XH_{.j} = u(H)$, where $H_{.j}$ is the j -th column of the matrix H . The number $u(H)$ is called **the expected utility** of the first player in the game H or **the value of the game** in X^* . Magnitude $u(H)$ has the nature of mathematical expectation. $X^* = (x_1^*, \dots, x_m^*)$ determined by different methods.

In the game against nature (1), **optimal decision-making** by the decision-maker or first A player means the optimal ranking of the candidates. Making an optimal decision by a player A using pure strategies in game (1) means choosing one of the candidates with the maximum guaranteed utility. For this, several classical optimality criteria are used. In the case when we know the probabilities of the natural states of the second player C , statistical decision-making criteria are used. If such probabilities are not known, then for a cautious player A it is better to determine the optimal decision by the maximin criterion of Wald - $\max_i \min_j u_{ij}$,

which simultaneously focuses on obtaining maximum benefits and minimizing possible risks. With this criterion, we find the largest element from the minimum possible elements of the profit matrix and, by means of them the only or several optimal candidates with equal utilities.

Valdi's or any other classical criteria will not be useful for solving our main task, since our goal is to touch every candidate to determine its priority. For this, we will use a new optimality criterion for problem (1) and with this criterion we will determine **the optimal decision of the player A**, the same as **the optimal plan for ranking the candidates**. First, we introduce the following notations and definitions for the game model H of task (1) (i.e. against nature).

The number $u(H) = \max_x \min_j XH_{.j}$ is the value of the game H , the same A player's **guaranteed expected utility** corresponding to $X^* = (x_1^*, \dots, x_m^*)$; $X^* = (x_1^*, \dots, x_m^*)$ is the

optimal solution of the game H , for which is achieved $u(H)$, and x_i^* is the probability of choosing a candidate a_i , i.e. a_i **the candidate's weight**; the number $\Sigma(a_i) = \sum_{j=1}^n u_{ij}$ is **the sum of the a_i candidate's grades**; $u(a_i) = x_i^* \sum_{j=1}^n u_{ij} \equiv x_i^* \Sigma(a_i)$ it is **the expected average grade of the a_i candidate**.

In the game against nature (1), the player's A consideration of nature (the player C) as a losing side is equivalent to the A player's implementation of the optimal candidate selection plan taking into account the most unfavorable conditions.

From the above definitions and notations, it follows that (1) the expected mean values of the active candidates $S_a \subseteq S$ (whose weigh or selection probabilities are positive) in the problem are clustered around the guaranteed expected utility $u(H)$ of the player A

Note 1. If the task requires the ranking of criteria $k_1, \dots, k_n$, then the strategic game model and lexicography are included in the task [7].

Let's establish a new criterion, which we call the **"expected average evaluation criterion"**.

Definition 2.1. The descending order of values $u(a_i), i = 1, \dots, m$ determines the order of the corresponding candidates a_i in the ranking

$$a_i \succcurlyeq a_k \Leftrightarrow u(a_i) \geq u(a_k), \quad a_i \succ a_k \Leftrightarrow u(a_i) > u(a_k), \quad a_i \approx a_k \Leftrightarrow u(a_i) = u(a_k). \quad (3)$$

Thus, according to the criterion (3) of the expected average evaluation, we should find the optimal solution X^* of the task (1) to calculate the expected average evaluations $u(a_i), i = 1, \dots, m$ of the candidates, and their descending order determines the place of the corresponding candidates in the ranking.

3. Examples

Example 1. Find the ranking of the candidates a_1, a_2, a_3 in the game H , where $u_{ij} \in [0, 6]; i = 1, 2, 3; j = 1, 2, 3$:

	k_1	k_2	k_3
$H = a_1$	3	4	1
a_2	2	3	6
a_3	5	0	3

Solution. $X^* = (0.5; 0.33; 0.1667)$ is the optimal solution of the given game and therefore all three candidates are active, and the value of the game is $u(H) = 3$. The expected average marks of the candidates are

$$u(a_1) = 0.5 \cdot \Sigma(a_1) = 4; \quad u(a_2) = 0.33 \cdot$$

$$\Sigma(a_2) = 3.67; \quad u(a_3) = 0.1667 \cdot \Sigma(a_3) = 1.33.$$

Because of $u(a_1) > u(a_2) > u(a_3)$, that's why $a_1 \succ a_2 \succ a_3$.

Examole 2. Let's make 4 students $\{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4\}$ ranking based on their grades $u_{ij} \in [0, 5] (i = 1, 2, 3, 4; j = 1, 2, 3, 4)$ in 4 subjects $\{k_1 = \text{Mathematics}, k_2 = \text{Physics}, k_3 = \text{Chemistry}, k_4 = \text{English}\}$.

Solution. Let's say that with the given estimates u_{ij} the game H has the following form:

	k_1	k_2	k_3	k_4
$H = a_1$	5	1	4	0
a_2	2	3	0	5
a_3	3	2	4	5
a_4	2	3	0	5

In this game $X^* = (0; 0.2; 0.6; 0.2)$ is an optimal solution and the meaning of the game $u(H) = 2.4$. The expected average marks of the candidates are $u(a_1) = 0, u(a_2) = 2, u(a_3) = 8.4, u(a_4) = 2$. Thus $a_3 \succ a_2 \approx a_4 \succ a_1$.

In this game, as expected, the dominated candidates a_2 and a_4 turned out to be equal. If it is still required to choose the most superior of them, it is necessary for the experts to make a slight adjustment in their assessments.

4. CONCLUSION

Game theory is a universal mathematical apparatus and the basis for managing intelligent systems. It studies game situations and how to make the best and fairest decisions in them. With the model discussed in this article, competitive candidates are evaluated by an expert using many criteria within the framework of numerically given scale in advance. consists of a matrix game and in it we find the optimal mixed strategy of the first player selecting candidates. We will determine the candidates' preferences by the expected average evaluation criterion.

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